

Islamic Approach to Reduce Inequality

Amirah ' Afifah Binte Mohamad Roslan (DL2415339)

Iman Qistina Binte Roslan (DL2411646)

Siti Rafe'ah Binte Omer (DL2417369)

Sumayyah Binte Zaini (DL2410882)

Kulliyyah of Islamic Revealed Knowledge And Human Sciences

International Islamic University Malaysia

LEED 1301: English for Academic Writing

Cohort 1

Madam Arinah Othman

14 June 2025

Waqf Helps to Reduce Income Inequality for the Muslim Community in Singapore

Singapore is widely regarded as a model of economic prosperity and urban development, known for its towering skyscrapers, pristine streets, and a thriving trade hub. Despite its status as a thriving country, Singapore continues to face challenges related to income inequality. While recent figures such as the slight decline in Singapore's Gini coefficient from 0.472 in 2010 to 0.444 in 2021, suggest some progress in narrowing income gaps, long-term trends indicate that inequality remains a pressing concern (Woo, 2022). Singapore's welfare approach prioritises individual and family responsibility over universal social policies. Ethnic minorities such as the Malays and Indians, which contribute to 82% and 13% of the Muslim population respectively (Yayasan Mendaki, 2022), are more affected than the Chinese majority due to differences in education and social opportunities. Resultantly, many Muslim households remain at the lower end of the income curve while foreign expatriates and higher income groups enjoy greater financial flexibility. In line with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 10, which aims to reduce inequality within countries, waqf, an Islamic welfare system, plays a vital role in funding social and religious welfare of the Muslim community in Singapore.

Waqf is an Islamic charitable endowment where assets such as property, land, or money are dedicated to community use under Islamic law (Rusyiana & Ali, 2024). The term originates from the Arabic word waqafa, it means "to stop or to preserve and designated for a specified and defined purpose" (Listiana & Alhabshi, 2020). Scholars describe waqf as the act of retaining property for charitable purposes, making it irrevocable and owned by Allah (AAOIFI, 2015; Kahf, 2003). In Singapore, the Administration of Muslim Law Act (AMLA) defines waqf as a

permanent dedication of property for religious or charitable purposes under Muslim law, with the Majlis Ugama Islam Singapura (MUIS) being the appointed waqf authority.

While donation funds from charity can support the needs of the Muslim community, waqf is sustainable due to the perpetual returns both in wealth and in the reward of good deeds.

Despite being a Muslim-minority country, Singapore has emerged as a country with productive waqf management as elaborated by Owais and Jawwad (2023):

The role of waqf in Singapore has evolved over time to help alleviate poverty among Singaporean Muslims. In the early years, Waqf funds were mostly used to construct mosques and other religious buildings. However, in recent years, Waqf funds have been used to support a wide range of social and welfare initiatives. For example, in 2017, the Majlis Ugama Islam Singapura (MUIS) launched a \$30 million waqf fund aimed at supporting the educational, social and welfare needs of the Muslim community. This fund was established to provide scholarships for underprivileged students, support for the elderly, and aid for those struggling with financial difficulties. In addition to supporting social and welfare initiatives, waqf funds have also been used to provide microfinance to the Muslim community in Singapore. (p. 63)

To further strengthen the efforts, MUIS had launched a multi-asset community waqf, named Wakaf Masyarakat Singapura (WMS), in 2024 to dynamically support multiple beneficiaries across generations and encourage wealth contribution from the community in the spirit of *fardhu kifayah* (communal obligation). Therefore, the returns from waqf can bolster financial resilience, target gaps in national measures and multiply *barakah* (blessing) for the

Muslims. In this way, waqf helps to reduce income inequality in Singapore's Muslim community by complementing government efforts, self-sustaining existing community resources, and catalysing long-term wealth distribution.

Complementing Government Efforts

Firstly, waqf plays a complementary role to government initiatives in Singapore by addressing specific needs in the Muslim community that may not be fully covered by public services. As a secular and multicultural state with strong emphasis on meritocracy, the Singapore government provides comprehensive services but does not address every religious or cultural needs. Therefore, waqf steps in as the Islamic resource to support needs with religious dimensions, such as in Islamic education and in other Muslim welfare needs.

One of the ways that the Singapore government provides financial support is through the Ministry of Education (MOE) funds in pre-university and university secular education for Singapore Citizens through schemes such as the Edusave Account and Tuition Fee Loans. However, Islamic education is privately funded and is not covered under national education incentives. Similarly, madrasahs are not fully funded by MOE and are dependent on the support from MUIS and the community for operation and development expenses. The lack of support for madrasah students and religious education from the government would restrict both the madrasah and students' capacity building regardless of potential. Therefore, according to Mohiddin (2019) and Rusydiana & Ali (2024), waqf is instrumental in helping to perpetuate Islamic education by providing financial assistance to good performing low-income madrasah students through awards and scholarships in both secular and religious subjects, as well as by supporting asatizah

development. To ensure a holistic education for young Muslims, the Islamic Education Fund (IEF) finances part-time Islamic classes as well for students from low-income families who may not be pursuing full-time Islamic education (MUIS, 2025). The waqf fund thus helps to bridge the gap in which government financial aids fail to address for the Muslims, either due to the religious nature or presence of competition within the wider community for secular studies.

Evidently, waqf in Singapore complements government efforts without overlapping as the fund targets gaps that are not fully addressed by national schemes. In this way, the efforts can parallel each other in promoting excellence for the Muslims in both religious and secular pathways. This helps to foster community resilience for the Muslims and strengthens the religious ecosystem, such as in the spheres of education and welfare, for a thriving Muslim society of the future within the bounds of Singapore's secular governance. As the mitigation of income inequality would inevitably take time and generations, quality education and opportunities focused on the Muslims are essential in an ecosystem of change in order to build human capital and accelerate upward social mobility.

Self-Sustaining Existing Community Resources

Secondly, by endowing assets that generate rental income or investment returns, *waqf* creates a continuous and self-sustaining revenue stream for existing community resources. Hence, waqf serves a unique solution through its model of long-term asset management. It is especially suited to Singapore's landscape, where land is valuable and rental yield can support recurring societal needs without exhausting resources (Mohiddin, 2019).

Singapore continues to benefit from the early *waqf* contributions made by its three main groups of *waqif*: Arab merchants, Indian traders, and donors from the Indonesian Archipelago. The first known *waqf* in Singapore was established in 1820, known as Waqf of Omar Mosque in Kampung Melaka endowed by Syed Omar Ali Aljunied. However, MUIS reports that since the 1970s, no new physical *waqf* assets have been established. This decline is attributed to factors such as rising land costs, limited awareness of *waqf*, increasing reliance on institutionalized cash waqf, and challenges related to state land policies (Mohiddin, 2019).

Despite these challenges, MUIS has emerged as a central authority in waqf administration, managing one of the largest pools of Islamic charitable funds in Singapore. According to data from 2013, mosques were the primary beneficiaries of local *waqf* distributions (47%), followed by religious schools (19%), and then the categories of welfare for the poor, burial services, and rice distribution (9%) (Hamber & Haneef, 2017). To support mosque development in particular, Singapore introduced a distinctive initiative known as Mosque Building Fund (MBF), which some consider to be as cash waqf. This system pools monthly contributions from the salaries of Muslim employees, with each individual donating a fixed amount based on their income. The funds collected are then used to construct new mosques or upgrade existing ones (Listiana & Alhabshi, 2020). Notably, the MBF has enabled MUIS to redevelop 22 mosques, raising a collected total of SGD 130 million (Mohiddin, 2019).

In summary, the waqf system has had a profound impact in Singapore, enabling the establishment of 13 out of 70 mosques and 4 out of 6 full-time religious schools (*madrasahs*). Through strategic land and fund management, as well as initiatives like the MBF, existing

community resources continue to thrive without reliance on one-off donations. This demonstrates how *waqf* can serve as a powerful model for self-sustaining development, ensuring the long-term support of Muslim community facilities in a small and crowded country like Singapore (Mohiddin, 2019).

Catalysing Long-Term Wealth Distribution

Lastly, waqf promotes the creation of community wealth in a long-term benefit for future Muslim generations. Initiatives by waqifs, their successors and generations who contribute a portion of his wealth to the community have managed to upturn the contrasting income disproportion of the nation. For Singapore's Muslim community, waqf emerges as a powerful and sustainable tool to address this imbalance. By enabling the transfer of wealth from the affluent to the underprivileged, waqf acts not merely as a charitable mechanism but as a catalyst for long-term, structured wealth distribution that empowers communities and fosters socioeconomic resilience within the Muslim community.

From the study by Listiana and Alhabshi (2020), the legacy of altruism from waqf in Singapore is apparent through the impacts of Arab-owned lands that were mostly endowed as waqf. The waqf income has not only benefited the Arab descendents across generations in Singapore, the beneficiary also covers those in Hadramaut, where the waqifs originated from, Saudi Arabia, Malaysia and Indonesia. Apart from being channeled to fund community infrastructure such as mosques, schools and others, portions of the income were also allocated to help the needy who may or may not be a family relative of the waqifs. From interviews with trustees and descendants of the waqif, we understand that waqf properties may also benefit

descendents when urgent help is needed on-demand, such as for medical cost in healthcare needs. Another trustee had also demonstrated the impact of waqf having benefited up to 4000 people in need in Yemen. As the waqf properties have been around for centuries, descendents have gained inspiration and belief in the legacy left by their forefathers through waqf, seeing it as a responsibility and trust (amanah) to honour for generations to come.

Therefore, waqf represents a uniquely Islamic yet universally relevant model for reducing income inequality. In Singapore's plural and pragmatic context, it functions as a socially embedded, ethically grounded, and economically effective institution. By enabling the transfer of wealth from individuals to the community and future generations in perpetuity, supporting essential services, and investing in human capital, waqf addresses both the symptoms and root causes of poverty. As such, it stands not only as a pillar of Islamic philanthropy but as a strategic tool for inclusive development and community empowerment. It is evident that waqf catalyses not just long-term wealth distribution, but also facilitates legacy altruism both in the material and spiritual needs of the future generation. When proliferated amongst Muslims in Singapore through the WMS, waqf can multiply blessings for the wider Muslim community.

Conclusion

Overall, waqf helps to reduce income inequality in Singapore's Muslim community by complementing government efforts, self-sustaining existing community resources, and catalysing long-term wealth distribution. It is thus essential to ensure that public education on waqf is sustained consistently and reaches the majority of Muslims in Singapore to harness its impacts both in material and spiritual wealth for the society. While MUIS had organised events during

the launch of WMS in 2024, the educational platforms should be diversified to ensure greater outreach beyond individuals in the religious or financial industries. This can be done through leveraging mosques, madrasahs and Muslim organisations for publicity, initiating a WMS ambassador programme for volunteers to speak at key community events, incorporating waqf into religious curriculum for deeper understanding on Islamic endowment, as well as sharing an annual WMS impact report to inspire the community. These engagements would promote waqf as the ideal mode for wealth distribution amongst Muslims, building communities of success.

From the Islamic perspective, waqf is a form of sadaqah jariyah (continuing charity), reflecting the value of birr (righteousness) and long-term community support. It provides lasting benefits by and spiritual reward through the redistribution of wealth and support for essential services. In Singapore, this reflects how Islamic principles remain relevant in addressing modern needs while strengthening community resilience and social justice. Allah revealed in the Qur'an (2:261), "The example of those who spend their wealth in the way of Allah is like a seed [of grain] which grows seven spikes; in each spike is a hundred grains. And Allah multiplies [His reward] for whom He wills. And Allah is all-Encompassing and knowing."

References

- Hamber, N., & Haneef, M. (2017). Waqf-Based Social Micro Venture Fund: A Proposal for the Malay-Muslim Community in Singapore. *Journal of King Abdulaziz University: Islamic Economics*, 30(1). <https://doi.org/10.4197/islec.30-1.3>
- Hasan, Z. (2012). *Shari'ah governance in Islamic financial institutions*. Edinburgh University Press.
- Islamic Religious Council of Singapore (MUIS). (n.d.). *Wakaf Ilmu – Contributing to education through Waqf*. <https://www.muis.gov.sg/Our-Services/Wakaf/Wakaf-Ilmu>
- Kahf, M. (2003). The role of waqf in improving the Ummah welfare. In *Proceedings of the International Seminar on Waqf as a Private Legal Body*. Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.
- Listiana, L., & Alhabshi, S. M. (2020). WAQF AND LEGACY OF ALTRUISM IN SINGAPORE: CHALLENGES AND DEVELOPMENT. *Deleted Journal*, 6(1), 116. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jebis.v6i1.19736>
- Mohiddin, M. N. (2019). WAQF DEVELOPMENT IN MINORITY MUSLIM COUNTRY: SINGAPORE'S EXPERIENCE. *Deleted Journal*, 2(1), 19–34. https://doi.org/10.24191/jipsf/v2n12019_19-34

- MUIS. (2021, August 4). Despite pandemic, wakaf continues to provide support to the community. Retrieved <https://www.muis.gov.sg/resources/media-releases/04-aug-21-despite-pandemic-wakaf-continues-to-provide-support-to-the-community>
- MUIS. (2025, February 21). *Part-time Islamic classes*. Retrieved <https://www.muis.gov.sg/education/part-time-islamic-classes/>
- Owais, M., & Ali, J. (2023). Waqf management reform: A pathway to alleviate poverty within Muslim societies. *Journal of Emerging Economies & Islamic Research*, 11(1), 57-70.
- Rusydiana, A. S., & Ali, M. M. (2024). Waqf in Non-Muslim Countries: A Case Study of Singapore. *International Journal of Waqf*, 4(1).
- Woo, A. (2022). Inequality in Singapore: The Hidden Poor. *LSE International Development Review*, 2(2).
- Yayasan Mendaki. (2022). *Singapore Malay/Muslim Community in Figures*. Retrieved https://www.mendaki.org.sg/resources_type/community-in-figures-2022/